

1 **A Lagrangian Time-Series Machine Learning Framework for Predicting**
2 **Concentrations and Exploring Drivers of Atmospheric Aerosols: Model**
3 **Development and Application to Cloud Condensation Nuclei in Marine**
4 **Boundary Layer**

5
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11 **Key Points**

- 12 • A Lagrangian time-series machine learning (ML) framework is proposed to better capture
13 the dynamic processes governing aerosol variability
- 14 • It achieves higher predictive skill for cloud condensation nuclei concentrations in marine
15 environments compared to conventional ML models
- 16 • Its more physically informed architecture enables identification of the controlling
17 processes and their characteristic timescales
- 18

19 **Abstract**

20 Atmospheric aerosols play critical roles in climate and air quality. Accurately assessing their
21 environmental impacts requires understanding aerosol abundance, distribution, and the key factors
22 and processes that control them. Although machine learning has been increasingly adopted in
23 predicting aerosol concentrations, its application in exploring underlying processes is limited, and
24 existing studies often fail to capture processes occurring during preceding days that substantially
25 shape aerosol populations. Here we develop a Lagrangian time-series machine learning framework
26 that better represents those dynamic processes. Three-dimensional back-trajectories of airmasses
27 arriving at the receptor site are derived using a physics-driven Lagrangian transport model.
28 Environmental variables along these air mass trajectories are then included as time-series input
29 features for a long short-term memory network to predict aerosol concentrations at the receptor
30 site. We apply this framework to multiyear cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) observations from
31 the eastern North Atlantic (ENA). The resulting model exhibits strong predictive skill and
32 outperforms conventional machine learning models. Moreover, the model trained solely on the
33 ENA data successfully reproduces a large fraction of CCN variability at a site in the South Atlantic,
34 indicating that it indeed captures the general processes driving marine CCN variability. Model
35 interpretation reveals that the seasonal variation of CCN over ENA is primarily controlled by
36 aerosol production associated with short-wave radiation, whereas the variation on a shorter
37 timescale is dominated by wet removal. This Lagrangian time-series framework, which is more
38 physically consistent with actual atmospheric processes, offers a powerful tool for predicting and
39 understanding the mechanisms of other atmospheric components.

40

41 **Plain Language Summary**

42 Atmospheric aerosols, i.e., tiny airborne particles suspended in the atmosphere, strongly influence
43 global climate and air quality. These particles are not only shaped by local environmental
44 conditions, but also by what the air mass experienced hours to days earlier as it traveled through
45 the atmosphere. In this study, we develop a machine learning framework that captures the influence
46 of air mass history in a physically realistic way. Instead of relying only on local conditions alone,
47 the model utilizes the time series of influencing factors along the air mass trajectory before arrival
48 as the input. Therefore, the model can learn the key processes acting along the trajectory,
49 improving both aerosol concentration predictions and identification of key controlling processes.
50 We demonstrate this approach using multiyear observations from the eastern North Atlantic. The
51 trained model shows strong predictive skills of cloud-forming particle concentrations and performs
52 substantially better than common machine learning models that use only local conditions or
53 average conditions along the trajectory. Based on the model, we identify the main factors driving
54 aerosol variability on different timescales. Although demonstrated here for aerosols, this
55 framework can also be applied to other atmospheric components that are influenced by air mass
56 history, such as trace gases or cloud properties.

57

58 **1 Introduction**

59 Aerosol particles are an important component of the Earth system and play critical roles in both
60 global climate and air quality (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). Aerosols influence the radiation budget
61 by scattering and absorbing solar radiation (i.e., direct radiative effects) and by modifying the
62 microphysical and macrophysical properties of clouds (i.e., indirect radiative effects) (Ackerman
63 et al., 2004; Albrecht, 1989; Li et al., 2022; Lohmann & Feichter, 2005; Twomey, 1977). The
64 aerosol indirect effects remain poorly constrained and constitute the largest source of uncertainty
65 in radiative forcing over the industrial period (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2021). In addition, elevated
66 aerosol concentrations from anthropogenic emissions, wildfires, and dust storms can lead to severe
67 air pollution in densely populated regions, posing a major global public health risk (Cohen et al.,
68 2017; Li et al., 2023a; Pöschl, 2005). These climate and air-quality impacts are closely linked to
69 aerosol abundance and physiochemical properties. Therefore, a predictive understanding of
70 aerosol properties and their controlling processes is essential for quantifying aerosol radiative
71 effects in past, present, and future climates (Carslaw et al., 2013; Gryspeerdt et al., 2023; Masson-
72 Delmotte et al., 2021), as well as for informing effective air pollution mitigation policies and
73 reducing associated health burdens (Huang et al., 2014; Zhai et al., 2021).

74 Atmospheric aerosols originate from a wide range of natural and anthropogenic sources that
75 include both primary emissions and secondary formations (Pöschl, 2005; Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016).
76 Their concentrations and distributions in ambient atmosphere are governed by a suite of complex,
77 nonlinear processes, such as particle formation, condensation growth, coagulation, chemical
78 transformation, dry deposition, and wet removal, all of which are modulated by a variety of
79 environmental factors. Despite extensive research, the key environmental factors and processes
80 controlling aerosol variability remain incompletely understood. This knowledge gap contributes
81 to large uncertainties in predicting aerosol concentrations and their impacts on climate through
82 aerosol-cloud interactions, as well as on air quality in diverse environments. Notably, chemical
83 transport models and global climate models often fail to reproduce observed cloud condensation
84 nuclei (CCN) concentrations and variability in remote marine boundary layer (MBL) (Block et al.,
85 2024; Fiddes et al., 2025; Gong et al., 2023; Niu et al., 2025; Wyant et al., 2015), indicating that
86 some key processes are missing or inadequately represented in models.

87 Previous studies have employed steady-state budget equations to identify the drivers of aerosol
88 variability from field observations (Ghate et al., 2023; Mohrmann et al., 2018; Tie et al., 2015;
89 Wood et al., 2012; Zheng et al., 2018). However, those equations omit many key processes and
90 are often oversimplified, limiting their ability to provide a comprehensive picture. For example,
91 previous studies usually neglected secondary aerosol formation when diagnosing the CCN drivers
92 in remote MBL (Ghate et al., 2023; Mohrmann et al., 2018; Wood et al., 2012), which has been
93 shown to make substantial contributions to CCN formation (Zheng et al., 2020a; Zheng et al.,
94 2018). Moreover, this approach relies heavily on prior knowledge of known mechanisms and
95 relationships, limiting their ability to gain new insights. Statistical methods, such as correlation
96 analysis with relevant environmental factors, have also been employed to infer key drivers
97 (Mansour et al., 2022; Sanchez et al., 2021). However, these methods are less effective at handling
98 multivariate non-linear dynamic systems and commonly lack robust validation.

99 Machine learning offers a powerful tool for uncovering complex nonlinear relationships in large,
100 multivariate datasets and has been increasingly applied in geoscience research (Chen et al., 2022;
101 Reichstein et al., 2019; Shen et al., 2023). Numerous studies have successfully used machine
102 learning to predict aerosol concentrations (Shen et al., 2024; Wei et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2022; Zhou

103 et al., 2024b). However, applications focused on elucidating the underlying physical processes
104 remain limited. While some studies have combined machine learning with model interpretation
105 techniques, such as partial dependence plot and Shapley values, to identify key influencing factors
106 (Grange et al., 2018; Hou et al., 2022; Houdou et al., 2024; Li et al., 2025; Song et al., 2022;
107 Stirnberg et al., 2021), their model structures generally do not adequately capture the
108 spatiotemporally dynamic nature of atmospheric aerosol processes. Fine-mode aerosols, which are
109 especially relevant for aerosol-cloud interactions and human health, typically have lifetimes of
110 several days, during which processes such as primary emissions, secondary formation, and
111 removal continuously shape aerosol population in the airmass as it travels thousands of kilometers
112 (Clarke et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2020). Consequently, aerosol concentrations at any given location
113 and time are influenced not only by local conditions but also by the processes in preceding days
114 during the transport. Most previous machine learning studies use instantaneous, local variables
115 alone as input features, thereby cannot adequately capture the processes during preceding days (Li
116 et al., 2023b; Nair & Yu, 2020; Stirnberg et al., 2021; Yao & Zhang, 2024). Although a few studies
117 have incorporated limited trajectory-based information (e.g., airmass cluster type, time fraction
118 over different surface types) (Hou et al., 2022; Li et al., 2025; Song et al., 2022), they still do not
119 capture the full temporal evolution of influencing factors. To improve predictive performance,
120 local aerosol composition measurements (Nair & Yu, 2020) and/or concentrations simulated by
121 chemical transport models (Nair et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022) are often included as input features.
122 However, such approach limits mechanism understanding and impedes the discovery of new
123 process-level insights, especially those that occur during transport.

124 To better represent the spatiotemporally dynamic processes, we propose a Lagrangian time-series
125 machine learning framework for aerosol prediction and analysis of controlling processes.
126 Leveraging long short-term memory (LSTM) networks (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997) – a
127 class of recurrent neural networks well-suited for time-series tasks – our approach incorporate the
128 temporal evolution of influencing factors along airmass trajectory as input features. Instead of
129 relying solely on local conditions, the model explicitly tracks atmospheric histories to predict
130 aerosol concentrations at the receptor site. We have applied this approach and trained a model
131 using long-term CCN observations in the remote Atlantic Ocean, the resulting model demonstrates
132 high predictive skill and strong generalizability. Based on the trained model, we further investigate
133 the dominant drivers of CCN variability and their characteristic timescales. This framework, which
134 integrates physics-driven airmass backward trajectory modeling with data-driven LSTM, more
135 faithfully captures aerosol evolution in the atmosphere and enables deeper process-level
136 understanding. Because all input features are derived from globally available datasets, this
137 framework can be readily extended to other regions. Moreover, it can be applied to improve the
138 predictions and investigate the drivers of other atmospheric constituents, such as gaseous species
139 and cloud properties that are strongly influenced by airmass history.

140

141 **2 Methods and Data**

142 **2.1 A Lagrangian Time-Series Machine Learning Framework**

143 As discussed above, the atmosphere is a highly dynamic system, and the abundance and properties
144 of aerosols at a given location are strongly influenced by a variety of processes in the airmass
145 during preceding days. The core idea of our Lagrangian time-series machine learning framework

146 is to emulate these atmospheric processes by: (1) tracing the air mass movement before it arrives
147 at the observation site, (2) extracting time series of relevant variables along the air mass trajectory,
148 and (3) using these time series as input to an LSTM model to predict aerosol concentrations at the
149 observation site. A schematic diagram of this framework is depicted in Figure 1.

150 Here, we assume a total of N samples and m input variables, with each input variable represented
151 by a time series of T timesteps along the air mass trajectory. For each sample, the input multivariate
152 time series $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times T}$, in which $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is a vector of all m input variables at
153 timestep t . The predicted target value $y = f_\theta(x)$, where f_θ represents the LSTM model with
154 trainable parameters θ . The detailed structure and calculation inside an LSTM model can be found
155 in Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997). Notably, the LSTM hidden states and memory cell states
156 at a specific timestep depend on the states at previous timestep and the input vector at current
157 timestep. This mechanism closely mirrors aerosol-related processes in the ambient atmosphere.
158 For example, in a given air parcel, the aerosol concentration at a specific moment depends on its
159 concentration at the preceding moment and the changes that occur in between, which is largely
160 driven by meteorological conditions, atmospheric chemistry, and aerosol dynamics at that time.

161 In this study, we use the Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT)
162 model (Stein et al., 2015) to calculate the 10-day air mass backward trajectory arriving at the
163 observation site for every hour during the studying period. The trajectory height at the observation
164 site is set to be 200 m, and the calculation is driven by the Global Data Assimilation System
165 (GDAS, $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$) meteorology fields (<https://www.ready.noaa.gov/data/archives/gdas1/>). With a
166 1-hour resolution between trajectory points, each trajectory comprises 241 timesteps (i.e., $T = 241$).
167 The selected features and procedures for extracting their values along each trajectory are detailed
168 in Section 2.3. The configuration, training, and evaluation of the LSTM model are described in
169 Section 2.4.

170 While a few prior studies have applied LSTM to air pollution forecasting, they are based on
171 different frameworks and still do not fully capture the atmospheric processes along air mass
172 trajectory. For instance, Wu et al. (2020) used past local time series – including the target variable
173 itself – to predict the $PM_{2.5}/PM_{10}$ ratio, which neglects the spatial movement of air masses. Other
174 studies combined convolutional neural network (CNN) and LSTM using past time series from both
175 local and neighbor sites (Qiu et al., 2023; Wen et al., 2019), which may implicitly account for
176 regional transport but still rely on past target values as inputs. This approach restricts physical
177 interpretability and limits application in scenarios when historical measurements of the target
178 variable are unavailable.

179

180
181 **Figure 1.** Schematic diagram of the Lagrangian time-series machine learning framework
182

183 2.2 Aerosol Measurements

184 We apply the Lagrangian time-series machine learning framework to train a model that predicts
185 CCN in remote MBL. The CCN data for model training are from the eastern North Atlantic (ENA)
186 atmospheric observatory (39.09° N, 28.03° W, 30 m above mean sea level), located on Graciosa
187 Island in the Azores, Portugal. Situated over 1,500 km from the nearest continent, this site offers
188 an ideal setting to study the CCN budget in the remote MBL (Wang et al., 2022; Wood et al., 2015).
189 Established and operated by the U.S. Department of Energy Atmospheric Radiation Measurement
190 (ARM) program since 2013 (Mather & Voyles, 2013), the site provides long-term aerosol, cloud,
191 and meteorological observations (Uin et al., 2019). CCN concentrations (N_{CCN}) were measured by
192 a cloud condensation nuclei counter (CCNC; Droplet Measurement Technologies), and data from
193 October 2013 to December 2023 are used in this study. Every hour the instrument cycles through
194 5 supersaturation levels (0.1% – 1.0%), maintaining each level for ~10 minutes. Here, we focus
195 on CCN concentration at 0.2% supersaturation, representative of typical maximum
196 supersaturations in MBL clouds (Gong et al., 2023). The raw 1-second resolution data were
197 averaged over the last 5 minutes of each 10-minute measurement window at 0.2% supersaturation,
198 resulting in an hourly time resolution for training of the machine learning model.

199 Several procedures are implemented to ensure the quality of the CCN data. These includes (1)
200 removing contamination from local anthropogenic emissions, (2) removing the impact of sea spray
201 aerosols from shoreline wave breaking (Zhou et al., 2025), and (3) checking and correcting for
202 long-term inconsistencies due to instrumental drift and malfunctions. Details of the quality control
203 process are provided in Text S1 in Supporting Information S1.

204 We also use CCN data from Ascension Island (7.97° S, 14.35° W, 340 m above mean sea level)
205 in the tropical South Atlantic to evaluate the model’s generalizability. These observations were
206 conducted during the Layered Atlantic Smoke Interactions with Clouds (LASIC) campaign (June
207 2016 – October 2017) using ARM’s Mobility Facility 1 (AMF1) (Zuidema et al., 2016). Similar
208 data preprocessing approaches are performed to obtain the hourly N_{CCN} at 0.2% supersaturation.
209 The final datasets include 40,054 valid hourly CCN observations from ENA and 8,594 from
210 Ascension Island, with the corresponding time series shown in Figure 2.

211

212 **Figure 2.** Time series of observed CCN concentrations (N_{CCN}) at 0.2% supersaturation (a) from
213 October 2013 to December 2023 at the ENA site and (b) from Jun 2016 to October 2017 at
214 Ascension Island.
215

216
217

218 **2.3 Input Features and Data Extraction**

219 A total of 22 variables that potentially influence aerosol-related processes and subsequent aerosol
220 concentrations are selected as input features for the Lagrangian-LSTM model. These variables fall
221 into three categories: surface parameters, meteorological conditions, and airmass states (Table 1).
222 The selected surface parameters capture major natural and anthropogenic emission of aerosols and
223 precursors. For example, the SO₂ emission flux (SO₂EM) provides continental and maritime
224 shipping sources of SO₂ and serves as a proxy for other anthropogenic emissions that are highly
225 correlated with SO₂ on global scale. Sea surface concentrations of dimethyl sulfide (DMS) and
226 chlorophyll *a* (CHL), along with surface temperature and wind speed, capture the marine biogenic
227 emissions (McCoy et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2024a). Surface wind speed is also a key driver of sea
228 spray aerosol production in open oceans (de Leeuw et al., 2011). The meteorological category
229 includes altitude-independent variables characterizing the regional synoptic conditions where the
230 airmass is located, while the airmass state variables capture the physical and chemical properties
231 at the same location and altitude of the airmass. These two categories together allow for capturing
232 the influences of regional synoptic conditions, boundary layer dynamics, free troposphere
233 entrainment, photochemistry, and aerosol wet scavenging, etc.

234 All input variables, except for surface type flags and airmass pressure, are sourced from globally
235 available gridded datasets, including remote sensing products, reanalysis datasets, emission
236 inventories, and machine learning-derived sea surface DMS fields (Zhou et al., 2024a). Therefore,
237 in-situ measurements are not required to obtain input data for the model. Detailed information of
238 each dataset is provided in Table 1 and Text S2 in Supporting Information S1. We try to exclude
239 the reanalysis concentrations of trace gases and aerosol species as input features because they can
240 be highly uncertain. More importantly, relying on these inputs would make it difficult to
241 investigate the processes that control CCN concentration with the model. However, we make two
242 exceptions: carbon monoxide (CO) and submicron dust (DUST). These species are relatively
243 chemically stable, better simulated in reanalysis, and more interpretable in terms of atmospheric
244 processes. CO serves as a tracer of long-range transport of biomass burning and anthropogenic
245 materials, while DUST indicates the presence and transport of mineral dust aerosols.

246 To extract time series of surface and meteorological parameters along a given airmass trajectory,
247 we perform a 3-dimensional (latitude, longitude, and time) matchup between trajectory points and
248 the corresponding gridded datasets. For airmass state variables (excluding pressure), the pressure
249 (i.e., altitude) is included as the 4th dimension, with data being interpolated to the pressure level of
250 the airmass. Furthermore, for high-resolution datasets (i.e., SO₂EM, CHL, and precipitation),
251 spatial dispersion of the airmass is accounted for by allowing the spatial search radius to vary with
252 trajectory time (i.e., the time relative to when airmass arrives at the site). Further details on this
253 procedure can be found in Text S3 in Supporting Information S1. As a result, each aerosol
254 concentration measurement is associated with 22 input time series, each with 241 timesteps. Given
255 that many variables exhibit highly skewed distributions, we apply a power transformation to make
256 their distribution more closely resemble a normal distribution or uniform distribution. The
257 exponential values for each variable are listed in Table S2 in Supporting Information S1. The
258 overall data distribution and its evolution with trajectory time of each input feature after the
259 transformation are shown in Figures S9-S10.

Table 1. Information on the input features for the Lagrangian-LSTM model

Category	Variable	Full name	Unit of raw data	Data source	Spatial resolution	Time resolution	Note
Surface parameters	WS	10-m wind speed	m s^{-1}	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	TS	Surface temperature	$^\circ\text{C}$	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	CHL	Sea surface chlorophyll <i>a</i> concentration	mg m^{-3}	Satellite remote sensing	$0.042^\circ \times 0.042^\circ$	1 day	
	DMS	Sea surface dimethyl sulfide concentration	nmol L^{-1}	ML-derived global daily distribution	$1^\circ \times 1^\circ$	1 day	
	SO2EM	SO ₂ emission flux	$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	CAMS emission inventory	$0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$	1 day	Combine CAMS-GLOB-SHIP and CAMS-CLOB-ANT considering temporal profiles and COVID-19 adjustment factors
	LAND	Binary flag denoting whether the point is above the land or not	unitless	Classified by the location of trajectory point	-	-	1-over land, 0-over ocean
Meteorology	SLP	Sea-level pressure	hPa	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	LTS	Lower tropospheric stability	K	Calculated based on relevant parameters from MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	EPV	Ertels potential vorticity	$\text{K m}^2 \text{kg}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	PBLH	Boundary layer height	m	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	SWGDN	Surface incoming shortwave flux	W m^{-2}	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	CFLOW	Low-level cloud fraction	1	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	CFMID	Mid-level cloud fraction	1	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
	LWP	Liquid water path	kg m^{-2}	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	1 hour	
PREC	Precipitation rate	mm hr^{-1}	GPM IMERG V07	$0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$	0.5 hour		
Airmass states	P	Pressure	hPa	HYSPLIT-derived	-	-	The input field for HYSPLIT is GDAS ($1^\circ \times 1^\circ$)
	T	Air temperature	$^\circ\text{C}$	MERRA-2	$0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$	3 hours	Vertical resolution: 72 levels

OMEGA	Vertical pressure velocity	Pa s ⁻¹	MERRA-2	0.625° × 0.5°	3 hours	Vertical resolution: 72 levels
RH	Relative humidity	1	MERRA-2	0.625° × 0.5°	3 hours	Vertical resolution: 72 levels
LWC	Liquid water content	kg kg ⁻¹	MERRA-2	0.625° × 0.5°	3 hours	Vertical resolution: 72 levels
DUST	Submicron dust mixing ratio	kg kg ⁻¹	MERRA-2	0.625° × 0.5°	3 hours	Vertical resolution: 72 levels
CO	CO mixing ratio	mol mol ⁻¹	MERRA-2	0.625° × 0.5°	3 hours	Vertical resolution: 72 levels; scaled by observations and EAC4

261

262 **2.4 Model Configuration, Training, and Evaluation**

263 Our model architecture consists of a single-layer LSTM as the encoder and a fully connected layer
264 as the decoder. Increasing the number of LSTM layers does not significantly improve the model
265 performance. To mitigate overfitting, a dropout layer is incorporated between the encoder and
266 decoder. The model is built based on the Deep Learning Toolbox of MATLAB R2022b.

267 Model training is based on data collected at the ENA site. Because the aerosol concentration over
268 remote oceans and air mass trajectory path do not change rapidly at hourly timescale, both input
269 and target data from neighbor samples are very similar (i.e., temporal autocorrelation). Therefore,
270 a block splitting strategy is adopted to ensure independence between training and testing data and
271 minimize information leakage (Zhu et al., 2023). Specifically, we set the block size as 1 month,
272 and 6 months in 2022 (Jan, Mar, May, Jul, Sep, and Nov) is used as the testing subset, covering
273 all seasons of a year. For the remaining samples, 15% of days are randomly selected for validation,
274 while the rest are used for training. Here we set block size to 1 day for validation set to balance
275 minimizing data leakage with reaching local minimum in training.

276 Prior to training, each input feature is standardized using Z-score normalization, and the target
277 variable (i.e., N_{CCN}) is log-transformed to approximate a normal distribution. We utilize Adam as
278 the optimizer with a learning rate of 0.005 and train the model with mini batches. L2 regularization
279 is also adopted to further reduce the risk of overfitting. The mean square error (MSE) is used as
280 the loss function. Training terminates when the maximum number of epochs is reached, and the
281 model parameters corresponding to the lowest validation loss are selected as the final model state.
282 Hyperparameter tuning for the number of hidden units, dropout ratio, L2 regularization factor, and
283 maximum number of training epochs is implemented via grid search. Additional details regarding
284 the tuning process and the selected hyperparameter combination can be found in Text S4 in
285 Supporting Information S1. To enhance prediction robustness, the training-validation split and
286 subsequent training process are repeated for 10 times (Holder et al., 2022; Sigmund et al., 2020),
287 and the final output is obtained by averaging predictions from this 10-member model ensemble.

288 **2.5 Conventional Machine Learning Models for Comparison**

289 To evaluate whether the proposed Lagrangian time-series model significantly improves prediction
290 accuracy, we also train four widely used conventional machine learning models for comparison:
291 random forest (RF), least-square gradient boosting (LSBoost), support vector machine (SVM), and
292 single-layer artificial neural network (ANN). Each model is trained with 14 different sets of input
293 data: (1) the final timestep of the input time series (i.e., local conditions at the ENA site, x_T), using
294 the same data sources as the Lagrangian LSTM model (“Base” in Table 2); (2) the same as the
295 first one, but replacing the data of 6 variables (10-m wind speed, sea level pressure, liquid water
296 path, air temperature, relative humidity, and precipitation rate) with in-situ measurements; (3-8)
297 averages of each input feature over the backward trajectory with durations of 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, and 10
298 days; and (9-14) exponentially weighted averages over the same trajectory durations, with the
299 weighting factor defined as $w_t = e^{\frac{t-\ell-1}{72}}$, where w_t is the weight for timestep t in a backward
300 trajectory with a length of ℓ hours. For the first two sets of input data, the land flag and air mass
301 pressure are excluded. The data split and model evaluation procedures are consistent with those
302 used for the Lagrangian LSTM model. Hyperparameter tuning is performed individually for each
303 model, with details provided in Text S5 in Supporting Information S1.

304 **2.6 Interpretation Methods**

305 We apply a permutation-based Monte-Carlo global sensitivity analysis to investigate the overall
 306 feature importance. Assuming we have two datasets \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{D}' :

$$307 \quad \begin{cases} \mathcal{D} = \{x^{(i)}, y^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^N \\ \mathcal{D}' = \{x'^{(i)}, y'^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^N \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

308 the input datasets $\{x^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^N$ and $\{x'^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^N$ are from the same population, and each contains N
 309 samples and is large enough to represent the characteristics of entire population. y and y' are the
 310 corresponding predicted outputs.

311 For each feature $j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, m\}$, a new dataset $\tilde{\mathcal{D}} = \{\tilde{x}^{(i)}, \tilde{y}^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^N$ is constructed based on \mathcal{D} by
 312 replacing the data of j -th feature in $x^{(i)}$ with those in $x'^{(i)}$ while keeping all other features
 313 unchanged, and the new outputs \tilde{y} are predicted based on \tilde{x} .

314 We then estimate the first-order Sobol' indice (SI_j) as a measure of feature importance (Sobol',
 315 2001; Sobol' & Myshetskaya, 2008):

$$316 \quad SI_j = \frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y'^{(i)} - C)(\tilde{y}^{(i)} - y^{(i)})}{D} \quad (2)$$

317 where C and D are the mean and variance of the concatenated vector of y and y' , respectively.

318 This analysis does not rely on the availability of true target. In this study, \mathcal{D} is created by using all
 319 input data from October 2013 to December 2023 ($N = 89,856$), and \mathcal{D}' is created by randomly
 320 permuting the order of samples in \mathcal{D} .

321 This method captures feature importance for overall CCN variability, including both short- and
 322 long-term timescales. To assess importance specific to a particular month of year (i.e., no seasonal
 323 variability), we repeat the process for each month of year separately. For understanding the
 324 dominant drivers for seasonal variability, we treat each month as a unit and apply the similar
 325 permutation-based global sensitivity analysis to the monthly-averaged data. Details of the
 326 treatment and calculations are provided in Text S6 in Supporting Information S1.

327 Furthermore, the Lagrangian time-series framework enables tracking how feature importance
 328 evolves along the trajectory, offering insight into the temporal dynamics of underlying processes.
 329 For each feature $j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, m\}$ and each timestep along the trajectory $t \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, T\}$, we
 330 construct a new input dataset based on \mathcal{D} , where the values of the j -th feature at timestep t are
 331 shuffled across samples while all others remain unchanged. Let y^* denotes the output of the new
 332 dataset. The root mean square deviation between y^* and y is used as a metric for the importance
 333 of the j -th feature at timestep t ($FI_{j,t}$):

$$334 \quad FI_{j,t} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y^{*(i)} - y^{(i)})^2} \quad (3)$$

335 **3 Results and Discussions**

336 **3.1 Model Performance**

337 **3.1.1 Superior Performance of Lagrangian-LSTM over Conventional Machine Learning** 338 **Models**

339 Conventional machine learning models yield RMSE and R^2 values for testing set $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$ in
340 the ranges of 0.197 – 0.257 and 0.248 – 0.577, respectively (Table 2). Models trained on local
341 conditions at the ENA site perform the worst, with all testing RMSE values exceeding 0.23 and
342 R^2 values falling below 0.39. These results support our hypothesis that aerosol concentrations are
343 significantly influenced by air mass history and cannot be accurately predicted using local
344 conditions alone. Models incorporating in-situ measurements exhibit modest improvements in
345 performance, which can be attributed to the lower uncertainties of in-situ data compared to
346 reanalysis and satellite-derived inputs.

347 Substantial performance gains are observed when incorporating information during preceding days
348 along air mass backward trajectories. Model performance initially improves with increasing
349 trajectory length but declines beyond a certain point. The optimal performance is achieved with a
350 trajectory length of 5 days. Furthermore, models that utilize weighted trajectory averages generally
351 outperform those based on unweighted averages. This likely reflects the diminishing influence of
352 earlier air mass history on the final aerosol concentration. Therefore, downweighting older
353 conditions helps improve model accuracy.

354 Among the four conventional models evaluated, SVM and ANN outperform RF and LSBoost,
355 achieving the best testing RMSE and R^2 of ~ 0.20 and ~ 0.57 , respectively. In comparison, the
356 Lagrangian-LSTM model further improves the performance significantly, achieving a testing
357 RMSE of 0.184 and R^2 of 0.620. These results clearly demonstrate that our Lagrangian times-
358 series framework better captures aerosol-related processes along air mass trajectory and
359 consequently has superior predictive skills relative to conventional static machine learning models.

360 **3.1.2 Weighted Resampling to Mitigate Data Imbalance and the Final Model Performance**

361 Since MSE loss function weights all samples equally, training is dominated by the most common
362 N_{CCN} range, causing the model to underemphasize rarer values. In our dataset, 84% of the N_{CCN}
363 values fall within the range of 50 to 300 cm^{-3} (i.e., $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$ between 1.7 and 2.5; see Figure
364 S8a in Supporting Information S1). Consequently, training of the model tends to focus on this
365 intermediate N_{CCN} range, resulting in poor prediction performance for extreme N_{CCN} values, which
366 are important for understanding aerosol-related atmospheric processes. As shown in Figure 3a and
367 3d, the model systematically underestimates N_{CCN} when the true value exceeds 300 cm^{-3} , with a
368 mean $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$ bias of -0.149 , equivalent to a 29% underestimation in linear space. Conversely,
369 for values below 50 cm^{-3} , the model overestimates with a mean bias of $+0.314$ in log space,
370 corresponding to a 106% overestimation in linear space. As a result, the predicted N_{CCN} distribution
371 is narrower and more concentrated around the intermediate range (Figure 3c).

372 To mitigate this data imbalance issue due to non-uniform N_{CCN} distribution, we implement a
373 weighted resampling strategy prior to the training-validation split to increase the representation of
374 underrepresented (i.e., extreme) N_{CCN} ranges (Chawla et al., 2002; Haibo et al., 2008; Yu & Zhou,
375 2021). Details on the resampling methodology are provided in Text S4 in Supporting Information
376 S1. This approach compels the model to better learn from rare events with extreme N_{CCN} values.
377 As a result, the predictive performance for these extreme cases improves significantly (Figure 3b).
378 The mean bias of $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$ is reduced to -0.116 (a 23.5% underestimation of N_{CCN}) for true
379 $N_{CCN} > 300 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and to $+0.178$ (a 51% overestimation of N_{CCN}) for true $N_{CCN} < 50 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Although
380 this resampling slightly degrades overall model performance metrics (RMSE increases from 0.184
381 to 0.198 and R^2 decreases from 0.620 to 0.604), it yields a more consistent performance across
382 N_{CCN} ranges and a predicted distribution that more closely matches the observations. These
383 improvements are replicated on a different testing subset (i.e., half year of 2021; see Figure S11),
384 suggesting that the benefits of weighted resampling are robust rather than coincidental. Therefore,
385 we adopt the model trained with weighted resampling as our final model for subsequent analyses.

386 As shown in Figures 4 and S12, the final model effectively captures the temporal variability in
387 N_{CCN} across hourly to seasonal timescales. Most of the pronounced increases and decreases in
388 N_{CCN} are reproduced, albeit with some discrepancies in amplitude and timing. For daily average
389 N_{CCN} , the model explains over 74% of the variance in both logarithmic and linear scales (Figures
390 S13-S14). Overall, given the inherent uncertainties in input datasets and the exclusion of local
391 aerosol concentration measurements as predictors, the model demonstrates satisfactory predictive
392 skill. The consistent model performance across different testing subsets further indicates strong
393 generalizability.

394

395 **Table 2.** RMSE and R² for testing set based on conventional machine learning models with different input data sets and Lagrangian-
 396 LSTM model with full time-series as inputs

RMSE	Local conditions		Averages along trajectory						Weighted averages along trajectory						Time series along 10-day trajectory
	Base	With in-situ measurements	1-day	2-day	3-day	5-day	7-day	10-day	1-day	2-day	3-day	5-day	7-day	10-day	
RF	0.257	0.250	0.236	0.229	0.226	0.213	0.224	0.239	0.233	0.229	0.229	0.209	0.208	0.212	0.184
LSBoost	0.245	0.239	0.223	0.217	0.212	0.210	0.219	0.235	0.222	0.218	0.212	0.206	0.207	0.213	
SVM	0.241	0.235	0.220	0.214	0.209	0.204	0.212	0.230	0.221	0.213	0.206	0.197	0.201	0.205	
ANN	0.252	0.243	0.220	0.211	0.203	0.205	0.214	0.228	0.222	0.210	0.202	0.196	0.197	0.203	
Lagrangian-LSTM															
R ²	Local condition		Average along trajectory						Weighted average along trajectory						Time series along 10-day trajectory
	Base	With in-situ measurements	1-day	2-day	3-day	5-day	7-day	10-day	1-day	2-day	3-day	5-day	7-day	10-day	
RF	0.248	0.296	0.365	0.398	0.415	0.490	0.432	0.345	0.383	0.403	0.397	0.505	0.510	0.489	0.620
LSBoost	0.309	0.350	0.432	0.458	0.484	0.496	0.451	0.369	0.436	0.456	0.485	0.514	0.505	0.481	
SVM	0.346	0.384	0.450	0.476	0.505	0.531	0.493	0.400	0.445	0.482	0.518	0.566	0.547	0.523	
ANN	0.284	0.337	0.456	0.506	0.541	0.533	0.494	0.416	0.449	0.512	0.548	0.577	0.568	0.539	
Lagrangian-LSTM															

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404 **Figure 3.** (a-b) Density scatter plots comparing observed N_{CCN} and predictions from the
 405 Lagrangian-LSTM models trained (a) without and (b) with the weighted resampling strategy. (c)
 406 Probability density functions (PDF) of observed and predicted $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$, based on models
 407 trained without and with resampling strategy. (d) Box plots of the prediction biases (prediction –
 408 observation) across different observed $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$ ranges for both models. In panel (d), boxes
 409 indicate the interquartile range (IQR), horizontal lines and circles represent median and mean
 410 values, respectively, and whiskers represent the minimum and maximum values within 1.5 times
 411 the interquartile range from the lower and upper quartiles. RMSE and R^2 values in panels (a-b)
 412 and bias values in panel (d) correspond to $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$. The data in all panels correspond to the
 413 testing set.

414

415
 416 **Figure 4.** Time series comparison of observed and predicted hourly N_{CCN} for testing set, based on
 417 the final Lagrangian-LSTM model developed using the weighted resampling strategy.

418
 419 **3.2 Model Interpretation**

420 **3.2.1 Feature Importance and Dominant Drivers for the CCN Variability over ENA**

421 The most influential factors associated with the overall CCN variability across all timescales over
 422 the entire measurement period are surface incoming shortwave radiation (SWGDN) and
 423 precipitation rate (PREC), followed by surface temperature (TS), liquid water path (LWP), sea-
 424 level pressure (SLP), and surface wind speed (WS) (Figure 5a). PREC emerges as the dominant

425 driver of the intramonth variations of CCN for most months, with the exception of July, during
426 which CO exerts the greatest influence (Figure 5b). LWP also plays an important role in the
427 intramonth variations throughout the year, typically ranking as the second leading factor after
428 PREC. CO and DUST notably influence intramonthly CCN variability in summer and winter,
429 respectively. In comparison, SWGDN and TS have moderate contributions to the intramonthly
430 variability, but they emerge as the top two drivers of longer-term seasonal variations, followed by
431 PREC (Figure 5c).

432 Given that SWGDN may covary with cloud-related variables (e.g., cloud fraction and LWP) on
433 short timescales at specific locations, its importance based on the LSTM model could stem from
434 correlations with cloud properties. To examine this possibility, we retrain the model after
435 excluding SWGDN from the feature set and observe a statistically significant degradation in model
436 performance (Figure S15). This result confirms that SWGDN provides distinct information that
437 improves the model performance. Furthermore, SWGDN has higher importance for overall CCN
438 variability than any cloud-related variables, and its short- versus long-term importance contrast
439 also differs from those of the cloud-related variables. Together, these results further demonstrate
440 that the significance of SWGDN reflects processes directly related to surface radiation rather than
441 a correlation with cloud properties. A previous machine learning study also identified SWGDN
442 as a key factor governing the variations of aerosol numbers in the Arctic region (Song et al., 2022).

443 SWGDN primarily influences the production of marine aerosols. For instance, solar irradiance
444 dose has been identified as a key controlling factor for the biological production and
445 spatiotemporal distribution of oceanic DMS (a key precursor of marine sulfate aerosols),
446 particularly in remote low- and mid-latitude oceans (Galí & Simó, 2015; Vallina & Simó, 2007).
447 Similarly, the biological production rate of isoprene, another important precursor of secondary
448 organic aerosols (SOAs), has also been shown to increase with solar irradiance (Gantt et al., 2009;
449 Shaw et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2023). Beyond biological processes, strong radiation can also
450 stimulate abiotic production of isoprene (Ciuraru et al., 2015; Cui et al., 2023) and various other
451 volatile organic compounds (VOCs) at the air-sea interface via photochemical reactions
452 (Bruggemann et al., 2017; Bruggemann et al., 2018; Mungall et al., 2017; Novak & Bertram, 2020).
453 The oxidation of these biogenic or abiotic reactive VOCs and subsequent formation of low-
454 volatility condensable compounds in the atmosphere are enhanced by elevated concentrations of
455 photochemically produced oxidants (e.g., HO·, BrO·) under strong solar radiation (Berresheim,
456 2002; Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). These oxidation products can play a pivotal role in new particle
457 formation and subsequent particle growth (Zheng et al., 2020a; Zheng et al., 2021). Consequently,
458 high SWGDN levels promote both the production and oxidation of aerosol precursors and the
459 subsequent formation of secondary aerosols, thereby enhancing the MBL CCN concentrations.
460 This mechanism appears to be a dominant driver of the seasonality of CCN concentration,
461 suggesting the existence of a potential negative feedback loop among surface solar radiation,
462 marine reactive gases, MBL CCN, and marine low-level clouds (Charlson et al., 1987; Vallina et
463 al., 2007).

464 The high importance of PREC and LWP underscores the critical role of wet removal processes in
 465 CCN lifecycle, consistent with prior studies showing that precipitation is a dominant factor driving
 466 the variability of N_{CCN} and cloud droplet concentrations in MBL (Mohrmann et al., 2018; Wood
 467 et al., 2012). At the ENA site, extreme low-CCN events have been linked to in-cloud coalescence
 468 scavenging during cold air outbreaks, where anomalously high LWP values were observed along
 469 the air mass trajectories (Wood et al., 2017). Additionally, aerosol budget equation calculations
 470 based on ENA measurements also revealed that coalescence scavenging is the dominant sink of
 471 CCN or accumulation-mode aerosols (Ghate et al., 2023; Zheng et al., 2018).

472 The importance of CO during summer reflects the contribution of long-range transported biomass
 473 burning and anthropogenic aerosols. This long-range transport has been identified as a sporadic
 474 but strong perturbation to aerosol levels at the ENA site and are consistent with the summertime
 475 peaks of wildfire activities in North America (Gallo et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2025; Wang et al.,
 476 2021; Zheng et al., 2020b). Similarly, the enhanced importance of dust during winter is linked to
 477 Saharan dust intrusions, which are often associated with cyclonic dust storms (Gallo et al., 2023;
 478 Logan et al., 2014). Additionally, the concurrent transport of anthropogenic pollutants from North
 479 Africa and Europe and their interactions with dust particles (i.e., chemical ageing) can further
 480 increase N_{CCN} (Astitha et al., 2010; Bègue et al., 2015; Gaston, 2020). Results from the drop-one-
 481 feature experiment reveal that removing either CO or dust leads to a significant decline in model
 482 performance (Figure S15), indicating their importance is not due to the correlations with other
 483 variables. While previous observational studies at this site have identified the influence of these
 484 continental aerosol sources in a few isolated cases, our study demonstrates that they exert
 485 significant impacts on CCN variability in particular seasons based on multi-year data. The
 486 substantially lower feature importance of WS than SWGDN and PREC suggests that the
 487 production of sea spray aerosols (SSA) plays a secondary role in the CCN variability, consistent
 488 with some of the earlier studies showing SSA has a minor contribution to CCN in remote MBL
 489 (Quinn et al., 2017).

490

491
 492 **Figure 5.** Feature importances (first-order Sobol' indices) for (a) the overall CCN variability, (b)
 493 the CCN variability within each month, and (c) the CCN seasonal variability. In panel (c), the
 494 boxes represent upper and lower quartiles of the 20 results, the horizontal lines and circles

495 represent the median and mean values, and the whiskers represent the minimum and maximum
496 values within 1.5 times the interquartile range from the lower and upper quartiles.

497

498 **3.2.2 Operational Timescales of the Dominant Drivers**

499 As discussed in Section 3.1, the influence of a specific feature on CCN predictions varies with the
500 time elapsed before air mass arrives at the observation site. Leveraging the time-series nature of
501 our Lagrangian-LSTM model, we examine how feature importance evolves along the air mass
502 trajectory and, in doing so, explore the operational timescales of the underlying controlling
503 processes. This analysis not only enhances the interpretability of the model but also contributes to
504 a more mechanistic understanding. Here we focus on the top two drivers of CCN variability (i.e.,
505 SWGDN and PREC) to illustrate this approach.

506 For PREC, the input data corresponding to the final two timesteps along the trajectory exert the
507 greatest influence on the predicted N_{CCN} , and the relative importance of earlier timesteps declines
508 rapidly (Figure 6a). For instance, the importance of PREC one day prior to arrival is only ~25%
509 of that at the final two timesteps. This result is consistent with the more localized effect of
510 precipitation, which can rapidly scavenge activated particles and efficiently reduce MBL CCN
511 population.

512 In contrast, the peak influence of SWGDN occurs ~10 hours prior to arrival, and its relative
513 importance remains above 0.4 even two days before arrival (Figure 6a). Given SWGDN's strong
514 diurnal cycle and its value being zero at night, we further perform this analysis for each hour of
515 the local solar time at the trajectory point (ToD) to rule out diurnal confounding. The results
516 consistently show the conclusion that SWGDN from ~10 hours prior to arrival is more important
517 than local SWGDN for CCN prediction, regardless of ToD (Figure 6b). Among all combinations
518 of different time-series timesteps and ToDs, the highest feature importance occurs when trajectory
519 time is ~ -10 hours (i.e., ~10 hours before arrival) and ToD is at midday (10:00 – 13:00) when
520 SWGDN is typically the strongest (Figure 6b).

521 This time-lagged influence of SWGDN is consistent with the role of solar radiation in driving the
522 production of marine reactive VOCs and their oxidations in the atmosphere. Photochemistry-
523 related CCN production involves multiple steps, including VOC emissions, production of low-
524 volatility compounds through oxidation, new particle formation, and subsequent growth to CCN
525 sizes, and therefore it takes some time. The reported global lifetime of atmospheric DMS with
526 respect to chemical reactions ranges from 0.8 to 2.1 days (Chen et al., 2018; Fung et al., 2022;
527 Wohl et al., 2024), though regional variability can be significant depending on oxidant levels and
528 meteorological conditions. The lifetimes of isoprene and monoterpenes are typically shorter,
529 ranging from 0.5 to 5 hours (Kilgour et al., 2024; Kim et al., 2017; Palmer & Shaw, 2005; Shaw
530 et al., 2010). Oxygenated VOCs produced through photochemical reactions at the air-sea interfaces
531 can persist on timescales of several days (Mungall et al., 2017), and a chamber experiment shows
532 that a 12-hour irradiation is required for these VOCs to be further oxidized and promote aerosol

533 growth from below 20 nm to ~50 nm (Bruggemann et al., 2017). Although our current analysis
534 cannot definitively pinpoint the chemical species or mechanisms driving the time lag in SWGDN's
535 importance, its consistency with established timescales for chemical transformation and particle
536 growth supports this interpretation.

537 **Figure 6.** (a) Normalized importance of SWGDN and PREC at each timestep along the trajectory.
538 Trajectory time is defined as the time relative to when air mass arrives at the site. (b) Dependence
539 of normalized importance of SWGDN on the trajectory time and the local solar time at the
540 trajectory point (ToD_{trajectory point}).
541
542

543 3.3 Generalization of the Model to Ascension Island

544 Beyond demonstrating strong predictive skills on unseen, independent periods at the same location,
545 the LSTM model, trained exclusively on data from the ENA site, also successfully captures a
546 substantial portion of the CCN variability at Ascension Island (Figure 7). Although the predicted
547 absolute values exhibit substantial bias compared to observations throughout the entire LASIC
548 campaign, the model explains ~50% of the temporal variability at an hourly resolution, effectively
549 reproducing most of the pronounced peaks and troughs (Figure 7a,c). The explained variance
550 exceeds 50% when evaluated on the daily averages (Figure 7b,d). This result is particularly
551 noteworthy given that Ascension Island (in tropical South Atlantic) is situated over 5,000 km away
552 from the ENA site (in mid-latitude North Atlantic) and experiences markedly different
553 environmental conditions.

554 These findings provide strong evidence that the model based on the Lagrangian time-series
555 framework has learnt key mechanisms that control CCN variability in remote MBL. While the
556 testing results in Section 3.1 confirm the model's ability to generalize temporally within the same
557 site without overfitting, they do not necessarily confirm that the model has captured the underlying
558 physical processes. The predictive ability at Ascension Island shows that the model generalizes
559 not only across data space but also in underlying mechanism space, underscoring the robustness
560 of the results from model interpretation.

561 The observed biases in absolute N_{CCN} values are expected, given the measurement uncertainties,
 562 differences in regional background concentrations, and potential variation in the sensitivity of
 563 N_{CCN} to specific processes across different environments. As such, while the model effectively
 564 captures relative variability, its direct application to predict absolute CCN concentrations across
 565 large geographic regions remains challenging and warrants further investigation or site-specific
 566 calibration.

567 **Figure 7.** (a) Correlations between observed hourly N_{CCN} at the Ascension Island and
 568 corresponding predictions from the model trained on ENA data. (b) Same as panel (a) but for daily
 569 averages. Results are shown on a linear scale, as the focus is on the consistency in overall temporal
 570 variability rather than relative deviation ratios at individual data points. (c) Time series of observed
 571

572 and predicted hourly N_{CCN} at the Ascension Island. (d) Same as panel (c) but for daily averages.
573 Note that the Y-axis scales are different between observations and predictions.
574

575 **3.4 Advantages, Uncertainties, and Limitations**

576 In summary, the Lagrangian time-series framework offers several distinct advantages over
577 conventional machine learning approaches. First, from a process-level perspective, our framework
578 is more physically consistent with actual processes governing aerosol evolution in the atmosphere.
579 While conventional models can use hand-designed features to incorporate earlier information
580 along trajectory (e.g., trajectory averages as shown in this study), such features are often subjective
581 and do not fully capture the spatiotemporal variation of aerosol processes along air mass trajectory.
582 In comparison, our framework exploits spatiotemporal dependencies in a dynamic system more
583 exhaustively (Reichstein et al., 2019), enabling more robust investigations into the controlling
584 processes and their operating timescales. Second, benefiting from the more comprehensive input
585 information and physics-sound structure, the model exhibits a stronger prediction capability and
586 is less susceptible to overfitting. The LSTM encoder extracts key information from a 2-
587 dimensional input matrix, compressing it into a 1-dimensional latent representation, which
588 intrinsically serves as a kind of dimensionality reduction and enhances model generalizability
589 compared to simply flattening the 2-dimensional input matrix and using each element as an
590 individual input feature. Third, this framework represents a paradigm for integrating physics-
591 driven and data-driven approaches. Here we utilize HYSPLIT model to generate air mass backward
592 trajectories, which resolves the spatial dynamics based on fundamental atmospheric transport
593 equations. While it is also possible to represent the spatiotemporally dynamic system with purely
594 data-driven approaches, such as a combination of convolutional and time-series networks (Qiu et
595 al., 2023; Reichstein et al., 2019), they are more computationally intensive and more difficult to
596 interpret. Fourth, all input data originate from globally available gridded datasets, without relying
597 on in-situ measurements. Therefore, this framework is highly transferable and readily applicable
598 to other regions. Moreover, the model structure is not limited to predicting aerosol concentrations.
599 It can be extended to investigate other atmospheric quantities such as aerosol size distributions,
600 trace gas concentrations, and cloud properties, particularly in contexts where recent air mass history
601 is influential.

602 Despite these advantages, several uncertainties and limitations remain and warrant improvements
603 in future studies. First, currently unavoidable uncertainties exist in input data, impose an upper
604 limit on model performance. These uncertainties stem from both air mass trajectory calculations
605 and source datasets. Trajectory uncertainty generally increases with time before arrival. The
606 uncertainties in gridded source datasets appear to have considerable impact on prediction, as
607 indicated by the significantly better model performance if incorporating in-situ measurements into
608 conventional models. Improving the accuracy and resolution of these source datasets is expected
609 to yield notable improvements in predictive skill. Second, the current set of input features may not
610 capture all relevant processes influencing aerosol variability. This limitation may be due to either

611 incomplete scientific understanding or the unavailability of suitable datasets. Future studies can
612 systematically test additional features to improve model representation of aerosol processes. Third,
613 the model performance and generalizability could be further improved by increasing the training
614 data volume. While the number of labeled samples (i.e., with valid target value) is constrained by
615 measurement availability, the pool of unlabeled input data can be much larger because all input
616 data are independent of in-situ observations. Incorporating an autoencoder architecture to get a
617 pretrained LSTM using all labeled and unlabeled input data could enhance its ability to learn latent
618 representations, thereby improving downstream performance (Liu et al., 2022; Sagheer & Kotb,
619 2019).

620 In terms of model interpretation, the current analysis does not fully disentangle synergistic or
621 correlated effects among input variables. Because mutual correlations can obscure the attribution
622 of importance, it is possible that the importance of a factor is misassigned to another correlated
623 factor. This might be one of the reasons why SWGDN exhibits strong importance but DMS does
624 not. Another potential reason is the large uncertainty in sea surface DMS dataset. To better resolve
625 these relationships, future work should incorporate advanced causal inference techniques capable
626 of identifying and quantifying causal drivers in high-dimensional, time-dependent systems (Runge
627 et al., 2019a; Runge et al., 2023; Runge et al., 2019b). Our Lagrangian time-series framework is
628 structurally well-suited for such causal analysis. In addition to identifying key drivers, it will be
629 useful to further assess the direction and magnitude of aerosol response when a factor is changed
630 or a process is perturbed, which can help quantify the impact of external forcings (e.g., human
631 activity, biomass burning) on MBL CCN population.

632 **4 Conclusions**

633 We propose a Lagrangian time-series machine learning framework to predict the concentration of
634 atmospheric aerosols and exploring the associated drivers. Given the atmosphere is a
635 spatiotemporally dynamic system and fine-mode aerosols exhibit a relatively long lifetime, the
636 aerosol concentration observed at a site is strongly influenced by the history of air mass prior to its
637 arrival. Our framework integrates the physics-driven air mass trajectory model with data-driven
638 time-series machine learning model to emulate these atmospheric processes. We obtain air mass
639 trajectories from HYSPLIT model, extract the multivariate time series of influencing factors along
640 the trajectories, and use these as inputs to an LSTM model to predict the final aerosol
641 concentrations. Trained on multiyear CCN observations at the ENA site, the model demonstrates
642 strong predictive skill during unseen testing periods, outperforming conventional machine learning
643 models trained with either local conditions or trajectory-averaged features. Remarkably, the model
644 also reproduces ~50% of the CCN variability observed at Ascension Island, which is over 5,000
645 km from the ENA site. This strong transferability suggests that the model captures key universal
646 processes governing aerosol dynamics over oceanic regions.

647 Model interpretation analyses reveal key drivers of MBL CCN variability over eastern North
648 Atlantic. Seasonal variability is primarily controlled by aerosol production processes associated

649 with surface short-wave radiation, while the short-term intramonth variations are largely controlled
650 by wet removal, with episodic but strong influences from long-range transported biomass burning
651 aerosols, anthropogenic pollutants, and mineral dust, depending on the season. The Lagrangian
652 time-series framework allows for further investigating the evolution of feature importance along
653 the air mass trajectory. Results show that precipitation within the last 2 hours has the highest
654 importance, consistent with the efficient aerosol removal by precipitation. In contrast, SWGDN
655 ~10 hours earlier exerts the strongest influence of the observed N_{CCN} , likely reflecting its role in
656 modulating the emission and oxidation of marine reactive VOCs, which subsequently affect
657 particle formation and growth to CCN size that take some time.

658 Overall, the proposed Lagrangian time-series framework provides a more physically sound
659 approach for capturing the complex, history-dependent evolution of aerosol properties compared
660 to static, conventional models. Although our current model does not yet fully disentangle all
661 governing factors and underlying mechanisms, it provides a robust foundation for advancing our
662 understanding of key aerosol-related processes including aerosol-cloud interactions. Furthermore,
663 because the input features can be derived solely from globally available gridded datasets and do
664 not require in-situ measurements, the framework is readily transferable to other regions or
665 extended to study other atmospheric constituents beyond aerosol concentrations.

666

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674

675 **Data and Code Availability Statement**

676 All aerosol measurement data and in situ meteorological data used in this study are available in
677 ARM data Archive (<https://adc.arm.gov/discovery/#/>). The MERRA-2 reanalysis datasets and
678 GPM precipitation dataset are available from the NASA Goddard Earth Sciences Data and
679 Information Services Center (<https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). The satellite-derived sea surface
680 chlorophyll *a* concentration datasets are available from the Copernicus Marine Service
681 (<https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/products>). All datasets used to construct global daily
682 anthropogenic SO₂ emission fluxes are available from the Emissions of atmospheric Compounds
683 and Compilation of Ancillary Data (ECCAD) website (<https://eccad.sedoo.fr/#/catalogue>). The
684 EAC4 reanalysis dataset is available from the Copernicus Atmosphere Data Store

685 (<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/datasets>). The HYSPLIT model and the GDAS
686 meteorological dataset used to drive the model are both publicly available from NOAA Air
687 Resources Laboratory (https://www.ready.noaa.gov/HYSPLIT_hytrial.php;
688 <https://www.ready.noaa.gov/data/archives/gdas1/>). MATLAB scripts for data processing,
689 machine learning model development, and model interpretation have been deposited to Zenodo
690 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18120652>).

691

692 **Conflict of Interest**

693 The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest for this manuscript.

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Supporting Information for

A Lagrangian Time-Series Machine Learning Framework for Predicting Concentrations and Exploring Drivers of Atmospheric Aerosols: Model Development and Application to Cloud Condensation Nuclei in Marine Boundary Layer

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Text S1. CCN data cleaning and quality control

Data cleaning for local contamination and influence from shoreline wave breaking

This study focuses on natural aerosol variability over remote oceans. Therefore, any perturbations to the aerosol observations caused by local emissions – those not representative of natural remote-marine processes – need to be identified and excluded from analysis. For our island-based CCN measurements, there are two major types of such perturbations: contamination from local anthropogenic emissions and the influence of sea spray aerosols generated by shoreline wave breaking.

Aerosol particles generated from local anthropogenic activities are predominantly ultrafine (diameter < 100 nm) and enriched in less-hygroscopic carbonaceous components, and therefore generally have little impact on N_{CCN} at the supersaturation of 0.2%. Episodes of substantial perturbation due to local contamination were identified by sharp spikes and anomalously high average N_{CCN} values within individual measurement intervals. The detailed screening criteria are provided in Zhou et al. (2025).

The ARM's ENA observatory is located 470 m to the north shoreline of Graciosa Island and is frequently influenced by the sea spray aerosol (SSA) emitted from shoreline wave breaking, especially during high-wave and onshore-wind conditions (Zhou et al., 2025). These nearshore SSAs can substantially elevate measured CCN concentrations. Periods when the ENA site was affected by this process were identified using wave height, wave direction, and wind direction, following criterion 1 in Zhou et al. (2025). In contrast, the observatory on Ascension Island is situated 340 m above sea level, and high-wave events in the surrounding ocean are much less frequent. Consequently, the influence of nearshore SSA on CCN measurements at this site is expected to be minor, and no additional data screening for this effect was applied.

Quality control for long-term data consistency

During multi-year observations, the CCN instrument may experience periods of instability, such as drift in flow rate and supersaturation. These issues can introduce systematic errors into the reported N_{CCN} values, thus increasing uncertainty in the target variable and negatively affecting machine learning model training and interpretation. To mitigate these impacts, we implemented a multi-step quality-control procedure that integrates measurements from a condensation particle counter (CPC), a scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS), and an Ultra-High Sensitivity Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS), to identify the periods with noticeable CCN instrumental issues and correct the affected N_{CCN} data. The raw hourly aerosol concentration time series from these instruments are shown in Figure S1.

The quality-control procedure is based on two assumptions: (1) given the high reliability of CPC, the measured total number concentration of particles larger than 10 nm ($N_{>10}$) is accurate and can serve as a reference for diagnosing systematic biases in the other aerosol measurements; and (2) although the ratio of N_{CCN} at a specific supersaturation, or the number concentration of aerosols larger than a specific size (e.g., 80 nm, denoted $N_{>80}$), to the total aerosol number concentration ($N_{>10}$) may vary on short timescales due to changes in aerosol composition and size distribution, its long-term seasonal cycle is relatively stable and does not change significantly between years.

Based on these two assumptions, we first assessed the long-term consistency of the SMPS measurements and scaled the SMPS concentrations (uniform scaling factor across all size bins) according to the ratio of $N_{>10,CPC}$ to $N_{>10,SMPS}$. We then compared $N_{>80,UHSAS}$ with $N_{>80,SMPS}$ and found that the UHSAS concentrations during its second long-term continuous measurement period (December 2021 – December 2023; Figure S1) were systematically lower, with a linear fitting slope of 0.74 (intercept = 1.36 cm^{-3} , $R^2 = 0.98$). Therefore, UHSAS concentrations during this period were corrected by multiplying a factor of $1/0.74$. For periods lacking SMPS measurements, we compared the series of $N_{>80,UHSAS}/N_{>10,CPC}$ (after applying a 1-month moving median to filter out short-term variability) with its multi-year seasonal climatology. This analysis identified two additional periods with substantial UHSAS biases: (1) 16 January to 13 July 2019, and (2) 14 November 2019 to 25 May 2020. UHSAS concentrations in these periods were scaled such that the 1-month moving median of $N_{>80,UHSAS}/N_{>10,CPC}$ matched its multi-year median. However, it

should be noted that the UHSAS concentrations during the second period were excessively low, with a large portion of $N_{>80,UHSAS}/N_{>10,CPC}$ values an order of magnitude lower than the normal range, implying large uncertainties in the corrected UHSAS concentrations.

Next, we identified four periods with substantial CCN measurement issues (P1 – P4 in Figure S2), during which both $N_{CCN}/N_{>80,UHSAS}$ and $N_{CCN}/N_{>10,CPC}$ were outside their normal ranges or exhibited continuous drift. Outside these periods, $N_{CCN,0.2\%}$ and $N_{>80,UHSAS}$ showed a strong linear correlation, with a slope of 0.88 (intercept = -7.60 cm^{-3} , $R^2 = 0.81$). The median of the $N_{CCN,0.2\%}$ -to- $N_{>80,UHSAS}$ ratio was also equal to 0.88. Therefore, this value (0.88) was used as the reference for CCN correction.

P1 corresponds to a 10-day period with strongly negative CCN biases, where the regression slope between $N_{CCN,0.2\%}$ and $N_{>80,UHSAS}$ was 0.45, thus a scaling factor of $0.88/0.45$ was applied. P2 exhibited a positive CCN bias, and P4 showed a gradual degradation drift. For these two periods, the scaling factor for each hour was defined as the ratio of 0.88 to the 1-month moving median of $N_{CCN,0.2\%}/N_{>80,UHSAS}$. CCN measurements in P3 showed anomalously large negative biases, and because the UHSAS data in this period were also highly unreliable, any correction would carry large uncertainties. As a result, CCN data from P3 were deemed invalid and excluded from subsequent machine-learning model training. The comparison between raw and corrected CCN data is presented in Figure S3.

Figure S1. Hourly time series of $N_{CCN,0.2\%}$, concentration of particles with diameters greater than 80 nm integrated from size distributions measured by SMPS ($N_{>80,SMPS}$) and UHSAS ($N_{>80,UHSAS}$), concentration of particles with diameters greater than 10 nm integrated from size distribution measured by SMPS ($N_{>10,SMPS}$), and $N_{>10}$ measured by CPC ($N_{>10,CPC}$) over the entire observation period at the ENA site. Data influenced by local pollution and shoreline SSA have been removed, but long-term data consistency quality-control corrections have not yet been applied.

Figure S2. Time series of $N_{CCN,0.2\%}/N_{>80,UHSAS}$, $N_{CCN,0.2\%}/N_{>10,CPC}$, and $N_{CCN,1.0\%}/N_{>10,CPC}$. Dots show the raw hourly data, and lines denote 1-month sliding window statistics. Thick black dashed lines indicate reference values: 0.88 for $N_{CCN,0.2\%}/N_{>80,UHSAS}$, and the multiyear median seasonal climatology for $N_{CCN,0.2\%}/N_{>10,CPC}$ and $N_{CCN,1.0\%}/N_{>10,CPC}$. UHSAS concentrations have been corrected using SMPS and CPC measurements. The four pink shaded regions (P1 – P4) denote periods with significant CCN measurement issues.

Figure S3. Hourly time series of raw and corrected $N_{CCN,0.2\%}$.

Text S2. Data sources of input features and preprocessing procedures

Satellite-derived CHL

CHL data were obtained from the Copernicus-GlobColour Level 4 gap free product (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L4_MY_009_104/description). This dataset integrates observations from multiple satellite sensors, including SeaWiFS, MODIS Aqua and Terra, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP and JPSS1, OLCI-S3A, and OLCI-S3B, and an interpolation procedure is applied to fill missing data (Garnesson et al., 2019). The product has a daily temporal resolution and a spatial resolution of $0.042^\circ \times 0.042^\circ$.

Sea surface DMS concentrations

Global daily sea surface DMS concentration fields were generated using a machine-learning prediction model (Zhou et al., 2024). Nine environmental variables, including CHL, sea surface temperature, mixed-layer depth, nitrate, phosphate, silicate, dissolved oxygen, surface incoming shortwave flux, and sea surface salinity were utilized as the input features. The original product developed by Zhou et al. (2024) covers 1998 – 2017, and here we extend the temporal coverage to 2023. The spatial resolution is $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$.

SO₂ emission flux

As illustrated in Figure S4, we combined several emission inventories and associated adjustment factors to generate a global daily anthropogenic SO₂ emission dataset: (1) CAMS-GLOB-ANT v5.3 (Soulie et al., 2024) (<https://eccad.sedoo.fr/#/metadata/479>), (2) CAMS-GLOB-SHIP v3.2 (Jalkanen et al., 2012) (<https://eccad.sedoo.fr/#/metadata/462>), (3) CAMS-GLOB-TEMPO v3.1 (Guevara et al., 2021) (<https://eccad.sedoo.fr/#/metadata/504>), and (4) CONFORM v2.1 (Dombia et al., 2021) (<https://eccad.sedoo.fr/#/metadata/545>). All datasets have a spatial resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$.

Continental anthropogenic SO₂ emission fluxes were obtained from CAMS-GLOB-ANT v5.3, which has a monthly temporal resolution. We applied sector-specific daily temporal adjustment

factors from CAMS-GLOB-TEMPO v3.1 to construct daily fluxes. Additional adjustment factors from CONFORM v2.1 were applied to account for emission reductions associated with COVID-19 lockdowns in 2020.

Shipping SO₂ emission fluxes were obtained from CAMS-GLOB-SHIP v3.2, which has a daily resolution. This product is derived from global vessel activity data collected through the Automatic Identification System (AIS) and the Ship Traffic Emission Assessment Model (STEAM) (Johansson et al., 2017). The impacts of both COVID-19 lockdown and the International Maritime Organization (IMO) 2020 sulfur regulation are already incorporated.

Figure S4. A flowchart summarizing the data processing procedures for constructing global anthropogenic SO₂ emission fluxes.

MERRA-2 reanalysis

As summarized in Table 1, 16 input variables were obtained from the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, version 2 (MERRA-2) reanalysis dataset (Gelaro et al., 2017) (<https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets?project=MERRA-2>). The spatial resolution of MERRA-2 is $0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ (longitude \times latitude), and the temporal resolutions of the 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional fields are 1 hour and 3 hours, respectively. There are 72 vertical levels for 3-dimensional fields.

Among these variables, lower tropospheric stability (LTS), defined as the difference between the potential temperatures at 700 hPa and the surface, was not directly available. We therefore calculated LTS using relevant MERRA-2 fields, including temperature at 700 hPa and surface-level temperature and pressure.

A comparison of the surface-level data within the grid cell containing the ENA site against in-situ observations revealed substantial biases in MERRA-2 CO concentrations ($CO_{MERRA-2}$, Figure S5a-

b). $CO_{MERRA-2}$ agreed reasonably well with observations during 2022 and early 2023, but exhibited pronounced negative biases with strong temporal variability during other periods. CO concentration from the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) EAC4 reanalysis (CO_{EAC4}) are more consistent with observations. However, the values usually have coarse numerical precision, resulting in a lack of short-term variability (example shown in Figure S5d). Therefore, we continued to use MERRA-2 CO but applied scaling factors to correct its bias.

As shown in Figures S5b and S6a, the 1-month moving average concentrations of CO_{EAC4} and $CO_{observation}$ at the ENA site were highly consistent, demonstrating the robustness of the magnitude and seasonal cycle represented by EAC4. Meanwhile, $CO_{MERRA-2}/CO_{EAC4}$ typically showed little variation along individual airmass trajectories (Fig. S6b), indicating that the fractional biases in $CO_{MERRA-2}$ were generally spatially uniform over large areas. Based on this behavior, we used the reciprocal of the 1-month moving average $CO_{MERRA-2}/CO_{observation}$ (when observational data were available) or $CO_{MERRA-2}/CO_{EAC4}$ (when observations were unavailable) at the ENA site as a scaling factor to correct $CO_{MERRA-2}$ along the entire airmass trajectory arriving at the site.

Figure S5. (a) Time series of CO concentrations from in-situ observations, MERRA-2, and EAC4. (b) Ratios of MERRA-2 CO concentration to observations ($CO_{MERRA-2}/CO_{observation}$) and to EAC4 ($CO_{MERRA-2}/CO_{EAC4}$) as well as the ratios of EAC4 CO concentrations to observations ($CO_{EAC4}/CO_{observation}$). Thin lines represent the raw time series (3-hour resolution), while thick lines represent the 1-month moving averages. (c) Comparison of the scaled MERRA-2 CO concentrations with observations. (d) Example illustrating the limited numerical precision of EAC4 CO data during 2018. All data correspond to CO concentrations at the ENA site.

Figure S6. (a) Correlation between 1-month moving averages of CO_{EAC4} and $CO_{observation}$ at the ENA site, corresponding to the last time step of the airmass trajectory. (b) Evolution of the distribution of the relative ratios along the trajectory. Here the relative ratio is defined as the ratio of $CO_{MERRA-2}/CO_{EAC4}$ at each time step to $CO_{MERRA-2}/CO_{EAC4}$ at the last time step (Trajectory time = 0 h) of the same trajectory.

GPM precipitation

Surface precipitation rates were obtained from the Integrated Multi-satellite Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) V07 (Huffman et al., 2023) (https://disc.gsfc.nasa.gov/datasets/GPM_3IMERGHH_07/summary). The dataset has a spatial resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ and an original temporal resolution of 30 minutes. For subsequent analyses, the data were averaged to an hourly resolution.

Text S3. Data matchup between airmass trajectories and high-spatial resolution datasets

Airmasses disperse during long-range transport, and uncertainties in the HYSPLIT model accumulate over backward trajectory calculations. Consequently, for a given trajectory point, the footprint of influence from a variable may extend well beyond a single grid cell containing that point. Therefore, using value in the single grid cell may not accurately represent the true influence at the trajectory point. This is particularly true when the grid cell is small, the trajectory time to the receptor site is long, and the spatial heterogeneity of the variable is high.

The spatial resolutions of CHL, SO₂EM, and precipitation are $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ or higher. Due to airmass dispersion and uncertainty in simulated back-trajectories, using values within such small areas along the simulated trajectory path can miss a substantial portion of relevant information, especially for the earlier segments of the trajectory. The footprint of the back trajectory, i.e., the

area influencing aerosols in the airmass, is expected to expand as the trajectory is traced farther back in time.

We implemented a varied footprint area for data matchup and extraction along the trajectory. Specifically, the radius of a circular region (R) used for data extraction increases with backward time (T_B), and the weighted average of all values within this area is calculated, with the weighting factor (w) decreasing with distance from the center (L). A schematic diagram of this approach is shown in Figure S7a.

To derive appropriate relationships between R and T_B and between w and L , we ran the HYSPLIT model in dispersion mode across four seasons in 2017. For each case, 500,000 particles were released and tracked backward for 10 days. At each trajectory time step, we derived the spatial distribution of particle density at a $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ resolution. Based on this spatial density map, we integrated both the area and particle number of grid cells from highest to lowest density until reaching 50% of the total particle number (i.e., 250,000), and the radius of a circular region with equivalent area was assigned as R . By investigating the results of all trajectories, we defined three R - T_B relationships representing different levels of expansion rates of the footprint (Figure S7b):

- Fast: $R = \begin{cases} 5.500, & T_B \leq 1 \\ 5.500T_B^{0.856}, & T_B > 1 \end{cases}$
- Medium: $R = \begin{cases} 5.500, & T_B \leq 6 \\ 0.656T_B^{1.162}, & T_B > 6 \end{cases}$
- Slow: $R = \begin{cases} 5.500, & T_B \leq 16 \\ 0.101T_B^{1.440}, & T_B > 16 \end{cases}$

where R is in km and T_B in hours.

From each spatial density map, we also derived a series of particle density isolines. For each isoline, we calculated the concentration ratio relative to the center grid (the grid with the highest concentration) and the spatial area it enclosed. The relationship between concentration ratio and equivalent radius of the enclosed area was used to define the w - L dependence. Synthesizing data across all trajectories, we applied inverse logistic functions to fit the 10th percentile, median, and 90th percentile of w values in 20 L bins versus $\ln L$, yielding three w - L equations representing different weight decay rates (Figure S7c):

- Fast: $w = \frac{1.178}{1+0.0200L^{1.348}}$
- Medium: $w = \frac{1.012}{1+0.0014L^{1.613}}$
- Slow: $w = \frac{1.035}{1+0.0020L^{1.341}}$

where L is in km. Combining the three $R-T_B$ equations and three $w-L$ equations resulted in nine configurations for data extraction. Model performance was evaluated across all combinations, and the medium-footprint/medium-decay combination provided the best results. This configuration was therefore used for the final model development and analysis.

Figure S7. (a) Schematic diagram illustrating the approach of using a varied spatial search area to extract data from high-spatial resolution datasets. Note the schematic is for illustrative purposes only, and the size of the circle and the shape of the weighting function do not represent actual values. The base map is from Google Earth Pro. (b) The dependence of R on T_B for three expansion rate levels. (c) The dependence of w on L for three weight decay rate levels.

Text S4. Hyperparameter tuning and weighted resampling strategy

Hyperparameter tuning for the number of hidden units (N_{unit}), dropout ratio (R_{dropout}), L2 regularization factor (L_2), and maximum number of epochs (ME) was performed using grid search. The search ranges are:

- N_{unit} : [40, 60, 80, 100]
- R_{dropout} : [0.2, 0.4, 0.6]
- L_2 : [0.0001, 0.0002, 0.001, 0.002]
- ME : [20, 30, 50]

This resulted in 144 hyperparameter combinations. The optimal combination was determined with the lowest testing MSE, which is $N_{\text{unit}} = 40$, $R_{\text{dropout}} = 0.2$, $L_2 = 0.0002$, $ME = 20$ for the model without applying weighted resampling.

To mitigate target data imbalance, a weighted resampling strategy was implemented to increase the representation of rare samples with extremely high or low CCN concentrations. A total of 200,000 samples were randomly drawn with replacement from the original dataset, with selection probability proportional to a weighting factor (yellow line in Figure S8a) dependent on the corresponding CCN concentration.

To derive the weighting factors, we first fitted the probability distribution of the original $\log_{10}(N_{\text{CCN}})$. Three candidate distributions (Gaussian, Gamma, and Burr) were evaluated, and the Burr distribution was selected because it provided the best fit. The Burr probability density function is:

$$f(x|\alpha, c, k) = \frac{\frac{kc}{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^{c-1}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^c\right)^{k+1}}$$

where c and k are the shape parameters and α is the scale parameter, which are 10.107, 4.309, and 2.555, respectively (red line in Figure S8a).

A broader Burr distribution was then created by reducing the shape parameter ($c_{\text{new}} = \frac{c}{m}$) but keeping the scale parameter and mode value constant (mode = $\alpha \left(\frac{c-1}{kc+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{c}}$). The reciprocal of this broader distribution was taken as the weighting factor. A lower m value corresponds to a stronger adjustment of the CCN data distribution. Three values of m were tested (1.1, 1.3, 1.5), and $m = 1.3$ was chosen considering the balance between improving the prediction accuracy for extreme values and maintaining the overall model performance.

The same hyperparameter tuning procedure was applied when training with weighted resampling. The best combination in this case is $N_{\text{unit}} = 60$, $R_{\text{dropout}} = 0.4$, $L_2 = 0.0002$, $ME = 20$.

Figure S8. (a) The probability distribution function (PDF) of observed $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$, the corresponding Burr distribution fitting (red line), and weighing factors for weighted resampling (yellow line). (b) The PDF of resampled $\log_{10}(N_{CCN})$.

Text S5. Hyperparameters of traditional machine learning models

Similar to that for LSTM model, a grid search approach was used to identify the optimal hyperparameters for the traditional machine learning models. Table S1 lists the hyperparameters and their corresponding search ranges for each model. The best hyperparameter combinations were determined separately for models using ENA local conditions as input and for models using trajectory averages as inputs. For the former, the input data for the grid search originated from the same sources as those used for the Lagrangian LSTM model (i.e., without incorporating in-situ measurements). For the latter, the input data were the weighted averages of 72-hour trajectories. All training procedures were performed using the Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox in MATLAB R2022b.

Table S1. Hyperparameters of traditional machine learning models. “Best value_local” and “Best value_traj” are the optimal hyperparameter combinations for the models using ENA local conditions and trajectory averages as inputs, respectively.

Model type	MATLAB function	Hyperparameters	Search ranges	Best value local	Best value traj
RF	fitrensemble	'NumLearningCycles'	10, 20, 500, 100, 200, 500	20	200
		'MinLeafSize'	1, 10, 100, 1000, 10000	10	1
LSBoost	fitrensemble	'NumLearningCycles'	10, 20, 500, 100, 200, 500	500	500
		'MinLeafSize'	1, 10, 100, 1000, 10000	1000	1000

		'LearnRate'	0.01, 0.1, 1	0.1	0.1
SVM	fitrsvm	'BoxConstraint'	0.1, 1, 10, 100	100	0.1
		'KernelScale'	0.1, 1, 10, 100	100	10
		'Epsilon'	0.0026, 0.026, 0.26	0.26	0.0026
		'KernelFunction'	linear', 'polynomial'	'polynomial'	'polynomial'
ANN	fitrnet	'LayerSizes'	10, 15, 20, 30	10	10
		'Lambda'	0.0001, 0.0002, 0.0005, 0.001, 0.002	0.0001	0.0002
		'ValidationPatience'	20, 50	20	50

Text S6. Deriving feature importance for seasonal variability

To assess the contribution of each feature to seasonal variability, we treated each month as a unit and applied permutation-based global sensitivity analysis to the monthly-averaged data. The original dataset for model interpretation $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathcal{X}^{(i)}, \mathcal{Y}^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^N$ can be grouped by month: $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathcal{X}^{(k)}, \mathcal{Y}^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^M$, where

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{X}^{(k)} = \{\mathcal{X}^{(i)}\}_{i=hk-h+1}^{hk} \\ \mathcal{Y}^{(k)} = \{\mathcal{Y}^{(i)}\}_{i=hk-h+1}^{hk} \end{cases}$$

Here, M is the total number of months, which is 123 in this study (from October 2013 to December 2023). h is the number of samples in each month. To maintain this number constant across different months, only the first 28 days of each month were taken into analysis, thus $h = 28 \times 24 = 672$. By calculating the average of $\mathcal{Y}^{(k)}$ (denoted as $\bar{\mathcal{Y}}^{(k)}$), we obtained a series of monthly averages $\bar{\mathcal{Y}} = \{\bar{\mathcal{Y}}^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^M$.

Next, the order of months in \mathcal{D} was randomly shuffled while keeping the intramonth sample order unchanged, generating $\mathcal{D}' = \{\mathcal{X}'^{(k)}, \mathcal{Y}'^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^M$ and its corresponding output monthly averages $\bar{\mathcal{Y}}' = \{\bar{\mathcal{Y}}'^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^M$. Then, for each feature $j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, m\}$, the data of the j -th feature in $\mathcal{X}^{(k)}$ were replaced with those in $\mathcal{X}'^{(k)}$ while other features were left unchanged, and the corresponding outputs were predicted, generating a new dataset $\tilde{\mathcal{D}} = \{\tilde{\mathcal{X}}^{(k)}, \tilde{\mathcal{Y}}^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^M$. The monthly averages of the output are $\tilde{\bar{\mathcal{Y}}} = \{\tilde{\bar{\mathcal{Y}}}^{(k)}\}_{k=1}^M$.

The importance of the j -th feature for the seasonal variability of CCN was quantified by the first-order Sobol' indice on monthly averages:

$$FM_j = \frac{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M (\bar{\mathcal{Y}}'^{(k)} - C)(\tilde{\bar{\mathcal{Y}}}^{(k)} - \bar{\mathcal{Y}}^{(k)})}{D}}$$

where C and D are the mean and variance of the concatenated vector of \bar{y} and \bar{y}' , respectively. This entire procedure was repeated 20 times to obtain statistics for FM values, as shown in Figure 5c.

Table S2. The exponential value of each variable for power transformation to adjust the data distribution

Variable	Exponent	Variable	Exponent
WS	1	CFLOW	1
TS	1	CFMID	1
CHL	1/2	LWP	1/5
DMS	1/2	PREC	1/5
SO2EM	1/5	P	1
LAND	1	T	1
SLP	1	OMEGA	1
LTS	1	RH	1
EPV	1	LWC	1/5
PBLH	1/5	DUST	1/5
SWGDN	1	CO	1/5

Figure S9. Distribution of each input feature after power transformation. The variable LAND is excluded because it only has two values. Insets show zoomed-in views to highlight the majority of the data. Distributions include data at all 241 trajectory time points.

Figure S10. Evolution of data distribution (after power transformation) with trajectory time for each input feature. Color indicates the number of data points within each grid cell.

Figure S11. The same as Figure 3 but for the results with half year of 2021 (February, April, June, August, October, December) as testing set.

Figure S12. The same as Figure 4 but for the results with half year of 2021 as testing set.

Figure S13. Performance of the final Lagrangian-LSTM model for daily average N_{CCN} of the testing set.

Figure S14. The same as Figure S13 but for the results with half year of 2021 as testing set.

Figure S15. Increase in RMSE on the testing set after dropping one single feature (a) without and (b) with implementing weighted resampling strategy. Box plots summarize results from 20 experiments – 10 using the half year of 2021 and 10 using the half year of 2022 as testing sets. Cases with increases of RMSE significantly greater than 0 ($P_{\text{right-tail}} < 0.01$) are highlighted in orange. For each box plot, the box indicates the interquartile range (IQR), horizontal line and circle represent median and mean values, respectively, and whiskers represent the minimum and maximum values within 1.5 times the interquartile range from the lower and upper quartiles.